

The evolution of Antenna : from a device to a technology

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Abstract—From spark gap radio to Starlink technology, engineers have shown an incredible ability to develop antenna to the point that it plays a key role in connectivity and globally in the present modern life. The paper reminds briefly the fundamentals of electromagnetics to easily introduce the antenna basics as well as how it has evolved since the end of the 19th century. New opportunities for antenna evolution are explored and mainly those offered by the emergence of metamaterials.

Index Terms—Maxwell, antenna, permittivity, permeability, metamaterial

I. INTRODUCTION

Through the article, a strong background is established to address antenna design topics by reviewing the fundamental concepts of electromagnetics (EM) in general and the antenna in particular.

The article is organized as follows. In section 2, a precise review of Maxwell equations through different forms with a focus on the constitutive parameters (permittivity and permeability). The concept of radiation is clearly defined and it is the entry point to define the antenna in section 3. In section 4, the properties used to qualify an antenna, their EM origin and their interdependence are clearly exposed. In section 5, evolution of antenna is presented through the different forms built by engineers and the opportunity offered to enrich more the antennas panoply by using metamaterials a new composite material introduced in section 6. Finally, in section 7, the main topics with a potential to achieve advances in antenna design are summarized and a conclusion is drawn.

II. ELECTROMAGNETIC LAWS

The fields \vec{E} and \vec{B} are the fundamental components (primitive fields [1, p. 40]) of the electromagnetics since they define the force \vec{F} (Newton) acting on a charge q (Coulomb), moving with a speed \vec{v} (meter/second) as described by the Lorentz force law :

$$\vec{F} = q(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B})$$

\vec{E} is the force per unit charge, called the electric field (volt/meter) and \vec{B} is defined in magnitude as a force per current unit called a magnetic induction field or the magnetic flux density (Weber/square meter).

A. Maxwell equations for microscopic fields

In the international system of units (SI) and a frame of reference, Maxwell equations are written in differential form as shown in table I [2, Tab. 18-1].

The two first equations express the intrinsic properties of the electromagnetic EM field (both \vec{E} and \vec{B}).

the two last equations link the EM field to its generating sources :

- A scalar field ρ is the volume charge density (Coulomb per cubic meter)
- A vector field \vec{j} is the volume current density (Ampere per square meter)

μ_0 and ϵ_0 are constants called respectively the permeability and the permittivity of vacuum. $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ (Henry per meter) and $\epsilon_0 = \frac{1}{\mu_0 C^2}$ (Farad per meter) with C the celerity of light (299792458m/s).

In the presence of matter, interaction occurs between EM fields and the matter, generating induced sources known as secondary sources or dependant sources due to polarization (\vec{j}_p the polarization current density and ρ_p the polarization charge density) and magnetization phenomena (\vec{j}_l the magnetization current density) in contrast with sources that exist without the presence of matter known as impressed sources or the primary sources. The sources generated by these two phenomena are bound sources in contrast with free sources due to an other matter response, the conduction.

$$\vec{j} = \vec{j}_p + \vec{j}_l + \vec{j}_{excit}$$

$$\rho = \rho_p + \rho_{excit} \quad \text{and} \quad \rho_p = -\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{j}_p$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu_0} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \vec{j} + \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \quad (4)$$

TABLE I
MAXWELL-HEAVISIDE FORM

In order to relate electromagnetic fields to only excitation sources (free sources) and hence to avoid computing the induced sources, new auxiliary fields are introduced \vec{D} (Coulomb per square meter) and \vec{H} (Ampere per meter) the electric induction (or the displacement or the electric flux density) and the magnetic field respectively.

$$\vec{D} = \epsilon_0 \vec{E} + \vec{P} \quad (5)$$

$$\vec{H} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \vec{B} - \vec{M} \quad (6)$$

Where \vec{P} and \vec{M} are the polarization vector and the magnetization vector related to the induced sources as follows :

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{M} = \vec{j}_l \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial \vec{P}}{\partial t} = \vec{j}_p \quad (8)$$

Maxwell equations can be rewritten in the Maxwell-Minkowski form as shown in table II.

B. Maxwell equations for macroscopic fields

The drastic variation in fields in space over an atom or molecule is not relevant [3, p. 33]. The relevant physical quantity is the average of field or source over a volume large compared to one atom or molecule. Such average quantities are the the macroscopic fields ($\vec{E}, \vec{B}, \vec{D}, \vec{H}$) and macroscopic sources (ρ and \vec{j}). Macroscopic Maxwell equations are therefore for these macroscopic fields and are grouped in two sets. The first set is already mentioned above in the Minkowski-Maxwell form (table II). The second set (table III) is what is called the constitutive relations [3, p. 39].

The relation between auxiliary fields and fundamentals fields is quite complex to establish in most materials (the most general behavior (\vec{D} and \vec{H} depend on both \vec{E} and \vec{B} such as chiral media).

However in substances other than ferroelectrics (when \vec{P} exist in the absence of applied fields) and ferromagnets (when \vec{M} exist in the absence of applied fields) and for weak fields , the

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{D} = \rho_{excit} \quad (11)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H} = \vec{j}_{excit} + \frac{\partial \vec{D}}{\partial t} \quad (12)$$

TABLE II
MAXWELL-MINKOWSKI FORM

$$\vec{D} = D(\vec{E}, \vec{B}) \quad (13)$$

$$\vec{H} = H(\vec{E}, \vec{B}) \quad (14)$$

$$\vec{j}_{conduction} = J(\vec{E}, \vec{B}) \quad (15)$$

TABLE III
GENERAL FORM OF CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONS(BIANISTROPIC MATERIALS)

medium is considered linear and the constitutive relation is written as convolution operation (in time domain) [4, p. 6]as follows:

$$\vec{D} = \epsilon * \vec{E} \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{B} = \mu * \vec{H} \quad (17)$$

$$\vec{j}_{conduction} = \sigma * \vec{E} \quad (18)$$

ϵ, μ, σ are respectively time varying permittivity, permeability and conductivity of the medium which are referred as constitutive parameters characterizing the medium. In general, they are function of direction of applied fields (isotropic vs anisotropic medium), the position within the medium (homogeneous vs heterogeneous medium) and the frequency (dispersive vs non dispersive medium). The constitutive relations is expressed as a product operation, only for frequency nonvarying characteristics medium (example vaccum). For time harmonic fields, the constitutive relations are expressed as product operation of the phasor vector fields ($\vec{E}(w), \vec{B}(w), \vec{D}(w), \vec{H}(w)$) and the phasor tensors ($\epsilon(w), \mu(w), \sigma(w)$).

Many models exist to emulate the EM response of matter. One reference model is Lorentz model where the movement of a bounded electron is seen as damped harmonic oscillation. The model is not only useful to interpret the EM response of insulators but to also compare between the materials characteristics as it will be seen in section 6. The resulting relative permittivity ϵ_r is given by the following formula :

$$\epsilon_r(w) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{w_0^2(\epsilon_s - \epsilon_\infty)}{w_0^2 - w^2 - jw\gamma} \quad (19)$$

ϵ_s and ϵ_∞ are respectively relative permittivities when the frequency is null and approaches infinity.

w_0 is the resonance angular frequency where the magnitude of ϵ_r is maximum and γ is the damping constant. The general chart of frequency dependency of relative permittivity is shown in "Fig. 1" as illustration. Typical values of w_0 for common dielectric materials is much higher (optic bands).

Finally, differential Maxwell equations are not enough to resolve EM problems if discontinuities in electrical properties are observed in some points mostly between different media since the derivative of the vector fields will not exist. Boundary conditions [4, Tab. 1-3] are used to fully qualify the EM problem.

Fig. 1. Plots of real part ϵ'_r and imaginary part ϵ''_r of relative permittivity for a material with a $\gamma = 0.5$ rad/s, $w_0 = 20\gamma$, $\epsilon_s = 2$ and $\epsilon_\infty = 1$.

C. General form of Maxwell equations

Based on symmetry and charge conservation principles of physic, scientists proposed a general form of Maxwell equations (table IV) in the presence of hypothetical presence of magnetic source besides the real physical electric sources [5, p. 69].

ρ_m is the volume magnetic charge density (Weber per cubic meter) and \vec{j}_m is the volume magnetic current density (Volt per square meter).

D. Radiation

The link between EM fields and the energy flow (power) exiting an infinitesimal closed surface or the Poynting vector \vec{S} is given by the following formula:

$$\vec{S} = \vec{E} \times \vec{H} \text{ (Watt/square meter)} \quad (24)$$

And hence, P_e the instantaneous power exiting a volume V , bounded by a surface S is:

$$P_e = \iint_S \vec{S} \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (25)$$

For time harmonic fields , the time average Poynting vector \vec{S}_{av} is :

$$\vec{S}_{av} = \frac{1}{2} \Re(\vec{E}(w) \times \vec{H}^*(w)) \quad (26)$$

The Poynting vector is the EM radiation and its magnitude is the radiated power density. For next sections, the article focuses on a particular device called antenna whose main characteristic is electromagnetic radiation in space.

III. ANTENNA AS ELECTROMAGNETIC DEVICE

To prove the existence of EM wave, Heinrich Hertz builds in 1888, the first transmit antenna as inductor and capacitor in parallel (resonant circuit) (left side of “ Fig. 2”) to transmit energy without medium to a reception circuit (loop antenna). Till beginning of the 20th century, an antenna is just seen as another components in a electric circuit. But when the first wireless communications had been tested, a clear distinction of antenna from other electric components is established as visualized in “Fig. 3”. Antenna is seen as device used for the transition of the EM fields from a guided medium (wires) to unguided medium (the earth atmosphere). For communication systems, antenna is designed to achieve a particular spatial pattern of the radiated power density. The first transatlantic radio link was established in 1901 by Guglielmo Marconi

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\vec{j}_m - \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (20)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = \rho_m \quad (21)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{D} = \rho_{excit} \quad (22)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H} = \vec{j}_{excit} + \frac{\partial \vec{D}}{\partial t} \quad (23)$$

TABLE IV
GENERAL-MAXWELL FORM

Fig. 2. Hertz's transmit antenna model.

using dozens of wires in an inverted pyramid to create a capacitor with the ground. The first radio transmitter was just a circuit turning on and off to transmit energy to a resonant circuit (LC), the antenna radio ancestor. The energy is transferred through an air gap when the gap voltage crosses the air breakdown threshold.

A. Formal definitions

According to the IEEE standard 145 for definitions of terms for antenna [6] , it is defined as follows :

“Antenna is part of a transmitting or receiving system that is designed to radiate or to receive electromagnetic waves”.

The international electrotechnical commission IEC defines the antenna as [7] :

“a part of a radio transmitting or receiving system which is designed to provide the required coupling between a transmitter or a receiver and the medium in which the radio wave propagates”.

From mathematical perspective and due to the fact that only permittivity and permeability of a medium that appear in Maxwell equations, an antenna is just a volume with a spatial distribution of its materials permittivity, permeability and conductivity and when fed with a specific excitation will produce a radiation pattern.

IV. ANTENNA CHARACTERIZATION

Antenna is designed to meet requirements imposed by the target applications (communication or sensing applications). These requirements are expressed as antenna properties. Under an operating frequency and polarization, directivity and impedance are the main electromagnetic properties of an antenna.

- Directivity of an antenna in direction of point p is the ratio of the radiated power density $\|\vec{S}(p)_{av}\|$ to

Fig. 3. Block diagram of a radio link.

the surface average radiated power over a sphere whose center is the antenna and passing through the point p . Points where the directivity is independent of the distance to the antenna, form the far field region of the antenna. Hence, all antenna centric spheres in the far region present the same spatial distribution of directivity called the radiation pattern.

- Impedance of an antenna is the ratio between phasor voltage and the phasor current at an interface (pair of terminal points) between the antenna and the feeder . The real part of the impedance describes the energy flow to the antenna (active power). Whereas, the imaginary part describes the fluctuating energy flow to and from antenna (reactive power). The existence of reactive power is due to unbalanced energy storage between the electric energy density w_e and the magnetic w_m over a space surrounding the antenna called the near field region.

$$w_e = \frac{1}{2} \vec{E} \cdot \vec{D} \text{ (Joule/cubic meter)} \quad (27)$$

$$w_m = \frac{1}{2} \vec{H} \cdot \vec{B} \text{ (Joule/cubic meter)} \quad (28)$$

Other existing properties are auxiliary properties. All related antenna’s electromagnetic properties can be organized in three classes [5, p. 672] as summarized in “ Fig. 4”.

The interdependence of gain, directivity, impedance has led to the inclusion of partial quantities relates to a specified polarization visualized in the “ Fig.5”.

V. ANTENNA DEVELOPMENT

Based on the patents database of the world intellectual property organization WIPO, more than quarter of million of antenna patents have been published. Indeed, engineers have designed different physical structures to achieve the required EM properties and others specifications such as: size , cost of manufacturing, robustness, system integration, power support. . . .

Fig. 4. Antenna electromagnetic properties.

From a briefly historical perspective, the first use of antenna is cited in the Greek legend where Archimedes uses a solar reflector (furnace) as a weapon to burn the roman ships. During the renaissance, European scientists have used the reflectors to build telescopes given the birth to two main topologies. The first one is invented in 1663 by James Gregory , a Scottish mathematician based on parabolic main reflector and elliptical sub reflector. The second type more compact invented in 1672 by a Frenchman Sieur Cassegrain where the sub reflector is hyperbolic [8]. After the discovery of electromagnetic waves and the need of directivity to increase the transmission range, optic reflectors topologies- instead of wires topologies- have been reused in radio bands and they are still employed in modern point to point microwave links “Fig. 6”.

The most important advancement in antenna has occurred during the second world war in which the German engineers have demonstrated a technological superiority in using antenna systems for new purposes : guiding aircrafts and missiles and in radio detecting and ranging RADAR. The Germans were able to bomb allies’ targets on the British island in darkness and without any visual contact based on directive radio antenna systems to create radio beams “ Fig.7”. A scientific officer named Reginald Victor Jones from the British air ministry had successfully turned the German technological superiority to an illusion by developing countermeasures to deceive the enemy pushing the Electromagnetic warfare to new levels [9].

Micro strip antenna is probably the last known revolutionary antenna topology. It offers a light weight, low profile and easy integration in printed circuit boards. Although, a French American engineer Georges Deschamps has analyzed the radiation losses in a micro strip lines in 1953, it is Robert Eugen Munson , an American scientist who introduces the micro strip antenna as new class of antennas in a paper appeared in 1974 “ Fig 8”.

Plenty types of antenna have been emerging “Fig.9”.

Fig. 5. Gain and Directivity flow chart [6]

Fig. 6. Cassegrain and Gregorian antennas

Fig. 7. sketch of a German beam transmitter "dipole array" [9]

Fig. 8. The first microstrip antenna designed by Munson [10]

Fig. 9. Antenna classification.

Based on the considered excitation sources to easily compute the radiation pattern, antennas are classified into two types :

- Type 1: it includes dipoles, loops, and helices. The excitation current distribution is known.
- Type 2: it include all aperture antenna such as slots, open ended wave guided, horns, reflectors, microstrips and lens antennas. The EM fields over a closed a surface (containing the antenna) are considered known. Equivalent sources (table V) \vec{j}_{eq} and \vec{j}_{meq} over the surface are deduced through Huygens theorem.

Besides, a group of different antenna elements can be arranged in an electrical and geometrical configuration to form an antenna array (example Yagi Uda antenna).

In antenna design field, engineers have intensively used different shapes of materials with nature provided permittivity and permeability. Materials science offers the possibility to design new materials with non observable properties in nature. These man made materials are the metamaterials. The application of metamaterials in antenna design opens new horizons for both applications and performances. IEEE [6] defines metamaterials as : "An arrangement of sub-wavelength material structures

that results in bulk electromagnetic material properties not found in nature or difficult to obtain naturally".

VI. METAMATERIALS

From historical view, the first person who discusses the opportunity of metamaterials in electromagnetics area is the soviet scientist Victor Veselago. He published a scientific paper [11] in 1964 titled "the electrodynamics of substances with simultaneously negative values of ϵ and μ " in which he exposed the different properties that can get a such material , although no known substance has manifested a negative permittivity and permeability. One interesting and demonstrated property is a negative refraction index which leads to the construction of what is called superlens based on left hand materials whose refraction angle is in opposite direction to the incident angle. An english scientist John Pendry is the pioneer to build a metamaterial. Based on the principle that a material is always composite of elements whatever they are atoms, molecules or microstructure called cell. The cells are stacked together to form periodic pattern that present an effective permittivity ϵ_{eff} and effective permeability μ_{eff} defined by equations 31,32 respectively for an isotropic metamaterial . The built structure mimics the polarization and magnetization of atoms or molecules but at large scale.

$$\vec{j}_{eq} = \vec{n} \times \vec{H} \quad (29)$$

$$\vec{j}_{meq} = -\vec{n} \times \vec{E} \quad (30)$$

\vec{n} the normal exiting the surface .

TABLE V
EQUIVALENT SOURCES

$$\vec{D}_{av} = \epsilon_{eff}(w)\epsilon_0\vec{E}_{av} \quad (31)$$

$$\vec{B}_{av} = \mu_{eff}(w)\mu_0\vec{H}_{av} \quad (32)$$

All the mediating phasor fields $\vec{E}, \vec{H}, \vec{D}, \vec{B}$ are averaged over the cell. Pendry demonstrates that a magnetic response of a

composite material built from non magnetic matter (copper) is obtained thanks to cubic double split ring structure as unit cell “Fig.10” [12]. Different values of μ_{eff} are achieved by just modifying the physical characteristics of the unit cell.

In article [13], an electric dipole is emulated since a strong response electric field is created thank to a unit cell constituted from copper as conductor and FR4 as dielectric with the shape and dimensions specified in the left side of “ Fig. 11”. The general frequency dependency of Lorentz model ‘s permittivity is retrieved (the right side of “ fig.11”) and negative relative permittivity is observed for a giga Hertz frequency range. This frequency dependency is now easily tailored to attain some targets (ex the resonance frequency w_0).

At last, metamaterials are not always obtained by periodic arrangement of structure but also by randomized structures. This last type can be obtained by mixing two substrates with different constitutive parameters to get new ones. In article [14], polymers are used instead of the habitual ceramics, to meet the flexibility requirement. Polymers are embedded with carbon nanotubes to improve the effective permittivity of the new obtained composite substrate.

VII. CONCLUSION

Through more than a century, antenna design has remained an exciting research topic and it is getting more interest in this era of ubiquitous connectivity when more challenges rise pushing the antenna designer to achieve higher performance in bandwidth to support high speed, in efficiency to reduce energy consumption, in size to ease integration and in exploiting the higher available bandwidth (millimeter waves and above). Introducing metamaterials in antenna, requires a better understanding of EM –matter interaction at bulk scale (cell). The advances of computing systems will make electromagnetics computation more efficient and precise to model that interaction. New functionalities in wireless communication such as MIMO (multi input multi output) or Sensing application (Radar,...) will require a configuration of an antenna array. Building these innovative antennas will require new

Fig. 10. Equivalence between a unit cell and effective permeability [12]

Fig. 11. Equivalence between a unit cell and effective permittivity [13]

manufacturing process. All the mentioned engineering and others have transformed the antenna to a technology.

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